

Distributed Power Control in Downlink Cellular Massive MIMO Systems

Trinh Van Chien*, Emil Björnson*, Erik G. Larsson*, and Tuan Anh Le†

*Department of Electrical Engineering (ISY), Linköping University, SE-581 83 Linköping, Sweden

†Department of Design Engineering & Maths, Middlesex University London, United Kingdom

Email: {trinh.van.chien, emil.bjornson, erik.g.larsson}@liu.se, T.Le@mdx.ac.uk

Abstract—This paper studies a distributed implementation of the total transmit power minimization problem for downlink (DL) cellular Massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems. In particular, we study the convergence of the optimization problem is solved in a distributed manner and further determine the set of parameters should be exchanged between base stations (BSs) to preserve optimality. Numerical results manifest that the distributed approach converges to the global optimum after a few iterations with the very high probability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive MIMO is considered as a key technology for 5G networks due to its great improvements in both spectral efficiency (SE) and energy efficiency (EE) over legacy networks [1]. Moreover, resource allocation problems in Massive MIMO are reported to have much lower complexity than that in small-scale systems owing to the fact that the utility functions only depend on the large-scale fading coefficients thanks to the so-called channel hardening property [2]. However, so far, most optimization problems have been formulated and solved in a centralized fashion [2], [3]. This requires the network to gather full statistical channel state information from all base stations (BSs) at one location in order to centrally allocate resources in every cell. It raises practical questions, especially for dense networks with many BSs and users, about backhaul signaling, scalability, and delays [4]. As a solution, distributed implementation has been proposed to deal with the above challenges by letting every BS simultaneously optimize its own available resources, while the central entity is used to exchange information among BSs to control interference [5].

A few recent works have applied distributed implementation concepts to apply for Massive MIMO, e.g., [6]–[8]. For the uplink (UL) transmission, a distributed max-min fairness problem for a two-decoding-layers Massive MIMO system is studied in [6] based on the existence of an effective interference function obeying the rigid conditions [9], [10]. By formulating a non-cooperative game, [7] proposed a distributed EE problem which has a Nash equilibrium. For the downlink (DL) transmission, by utilizing the UL-DL duality, [8] proposed a distributed framework for a total transmit power minimization problem while seeking the optimal precoding

vectors which are functions of small-scale fading. Even though the optimal precoding vectors provides certain gains, the algorithm [8] suffers from the fact that small-scale fading varies fast and it also does not inherit the near optimality of linear precoding schemes in Massive MIMO. Furthermore, the previous algorithms assumed that BSs has fully access to the channel statistics of the neighboring cells [6] or all the other BSs [7], [8] which may require heavy signaling in the backhaul since users move and the active users change. To the best of our knowledge, no previous work explicitly investigates what information should be exchanged between BSs in Massive MIMO.

In this paper, we consider the DL transmission of Massive MIMO systems with maximum ratio (MR) or zero forcing (ZF) precoding. We study a distributed algorithm that minimizes the total transmit power across the network while maintaining a required quality of service (QoS) for every user. We further compare the distributed algorithm and its centralized counterpart to answer two following fundamental questions: i) Can the distributed implementation achieve the optimal solution to the centralized counterpart? ii) Which subset of parameters should be shared by BSs to maintain the optimal solution? iii) How can we limit complexity and backhaul signaling for distributed implementation?

Notations: Upper/lower bold letters are used for matrices/vectors. $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$ denotes the expectation of a random variable, while $\mathcal{CN}(\cdot, \cdot)$ stands for the circularly symmetric Gaussian distribution. $\|\cdot\|$ is Euclidean norm.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a cellular Massive MIMO system comprising of L cells, each having a BS equipped with M antennas and serving K users. The system operates according to a time division duplex (TDD) protocol. The time-frequency resources are divided into coherence intervals of τ_c symbols where the channels are assumed to be static and frequency flat. During the UL training phase, each coherence interval dedicates τ_p symbols for pilot transmission. If we assume that the same set of K orthonormal pilot signals is reused in each cell wherein user k in cell l allocates the power $\hat{p}_{l,k} > 0$ to its pilot signal, then $\tau_p = K$. In this paper, the channel between user k in cell i and BS l , is assumed to be uncorrelated Rayleigh fading,

$$\mathbf{h}_{i,k}^l \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \beta_{i,k}^l \mathbf{I}_M), \quad (1)$$

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where $\beta_{i,k}^l$ is the large-scale fading coefficient. Using minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimation [11], the channel estimate is distributed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{i,k}^l \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \gamma_{i,k}^l \mathbf{I}_M), \quad (2)$$

where the variance $\gamma_{i,k}^l$ is

$$\gamma_{i,k}^l = \frac{\hat{p}_{i,k} \tau_p (\beta_{i,k}^l)^2}{\sum_{i'=1}^L \hat{p}_{i',k} \tau_p \beta_{i',k}^l + \sigma_{\text{UL}}^2} \quad (3)$$

and σ_{UL}^2 is the variance of the UL Gaussian noise. In this paper, the channel estimates are used to construct the linear precoding vectors for the DL data transmission.

A. Downlink Data Transmission

In the DL data transmission, BS l transmits a Gaussian signal $s_{l,k}$ to user k with $\mathbb{E}\{|s_{l,k}|^2\} = 1$. The received baseband signal at user k in cell l is

$$y_{l,k} = \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^K \sqrt{\rho_{i,t}} (\mathbf{h}_{l,k}^i)^H \mathbf{w}_{i,t} s_{i,t} + n_{l,k}, \quad (4)$$

where the additive noise is $n_{l,k} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{\text{DL}}^2)$, $\rho_{i,t}$ is the power allocated to user t in cell i for transmission of the data symbol $s_{i,t}$ and $\mathbf{w}_{i,t}$ is the corresponding normalized linear precoding vector. The closed-form expression for the lower bound on the DL ergodic rate with MR or ZF precoding is in Lemma 1.

Lemma 1. [12, Corollary 3] *In the DL, the closed-form expression for the ergodic rate of user k in cell l is*

$$R_{l,k} = \left(1 - \frac{\tau_p}{\tau_c}\right) \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_{l,k}), \quad (5)$$

where the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), denoted by $\text{SINR}_{l,k}$, is

$$\text{SINR}_{l,k} = \frac{G \rho_{l,k} \gamma_{l,k}^l}{G \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L \rho_{i,k} \gamma_{i,k}^i + \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^K \rho_{i,t} z_{l,k}^i + \sigma_{\text{DL}}^2}. \quad (6)$$

The parameters G and $z_{l,k}^i$ are specified by the precoding scheme. MR precoding gives $G = M$ and $z_{l,k}^i = \beta_{l,k}^i$, while ZF precoding gives $G = M - K$ and $z_{l,k}^i = \beta_{l,k}^i - \gamma_{l,k}^i$.

B. Total Transmit Power Minimization Problem

As shown in [2], the transmit power at BS l is computed from the transmit powers as $\sum_{k=1}^K \rho_{l,k}$, $\forall l$. The total transmit power minimization problem of the L BSs subject to the certain QoS requirements for all users and the transmit power constraint at every BS is

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{\rho_{l,k} \geq 0\}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^K \rho_{l,k} \\ & \text{subject to} && R_{l,k} \geq \xi_{l,k}, \forall l, k, \\ & && \sum_{t=1}^K \rho_{l,t} \leq P_{\max,l}, \forall l, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 1: Distributed implementation of problem (8).

where $\xi_{l,k}$ is the QoS requirement of user k in cell l and $P_{\max,l}$ is the maximum transmit power at BS l . Converting from the SE requirements to the corresponding SINR values, i.e., set $\hat{\xi}_{l,k} = 2^{\xi_{l,k}} - 1$, (7) is reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{\rho_{l,k} \geq 0\}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^K \rho_{l,k} \\ & \text{subject to} && \text{SINR}_{l,k} \geq \hat{\xi}_{l,k}, \forall l, k, \\ & && \sum_{t=1}^K \rho_{l,t} \leq P_{\max,l}, \forall l. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Since problem (8) is a linear program, its optimal solution can be obtained in polynomial time by an interior-point algorithm, e.g., using CVX [13]. The centralized implementation requires the KL^2 large-scale fading coefficients of all channels (i.e., $\beta_{i,k}^l, \forall i, k, l$), the KL^2 variances of all the channel estimates (i.e., $\gamma_{i,k}^l, \forall i, k, l$), and the KL QoS requirements of all users to be gathered at one central station that can solve (8) to obtain the optimal power control (i.e., $\hat{\xi}_{l,k}, \forall l, k$). The optimal power solution then needs to be shared back to the BSs with requiring the KL more signaling on the backhaul. Alternatively, if every BS acquires $2K(L-1)^2 + K(L-1)$ coefficients from the other BSs, (8) can be then locally solved. This removes the need to send the solution over the backhaul and it is a basic form of distributed implementation.

III. DISTRIBUTED IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, a distributed implementation of (8) is proposed based on dual decomposition. Its convergence and the computational complexity are also investigated.

A. Assumptions for Distributed Implementation

The proposed distributed implementation for problem (8) is based on two levels of optimization: a master level and the L sublevels as schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. At Sublevel l , BS l will locally optimize the transmit powers to its K users utilizing the partial information. The following assumptions are made to allocate power for the DL transmission: 1) BS l possesses the statistical information including the large-scale fading coefficients $\beta_{i,k}^l$ and the channel estimate variance $\gamma_{i,k}^l$, of the K local users. 2) BS l has the statistical information of the $K(L-1)$ interfering users, i.e., $\beta_{i,k}^l, \gamma_{i,k}^l, \forall k, i \neq l$. 3) BS l jointly optimizes the DL powers allocated to its K local users based on the above prior information. 4) The inter-cell interference is considered as consistency parameters. They are the only information needed to exchange between BSs and will be defined hereafter.

B. Distributed Implementation by Dual Decomposition

Since the cost function in (8) is not strictly convex, a standard dual decomposition implementation is not guaranteed to converge [14].¹ Thus, in order to ensure the convergence of the distributed implementation, we will convert (8) into a convex problem which involves a strictly convex cost function by introducing a new variable $\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}$ such as $\rho_{l,k} = \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2, \forall l, k$. The SINR value of user k in cell l is

$$\text{SINR}_{l,k} = \frac{G\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^l}{\sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L \left(G\tilde{\rho}_{i,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^i + \sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{i,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t \right) + \sigma_{\text{DL}}^2}. \quad (9)$$

The first term in the denominator of (9) represents the mutual non-coherent interference of the K local users served by BS l . Hence, BS l can locally evaluate this term. The second term includes the coherent interference caused by the users utilizing nonorthogonal pilot signals and the non-coherent interference from all users in the other cells. If BS l wishes to evaluate the SE of each local user, it will need to obtain this information from the other $L-1$ BSs (i.e., the prices in Fig. 1) to estimate the second part. In order to reduce the amount of exchanged information among BSs, we introduce so-called consistency variables $\theta_{l,k}^i$ and $\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i$ which represent the exact and believed value of $G\tilde{\rho}_{i,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^i + \sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{i,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t$, respectively. Thus, (8) is reformulated as

$$\underset{\{\tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \geq 0, \theta_{l,k}^i \geq 0, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i \geq 0\}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{i,t}^2 \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \frac{G\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^l}{\sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L (\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i)^2 + \sigma_{\text{DL}}^2} \geq \hat{\xi}_{l,k}, \forall l, k, \quad (10b)$$

$$G\tilde{\rho}_{i,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^i + \sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{i,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t \leq (\theta_{l,k}^i)^2, \forall l, i, k, i \neq l, \quad (10c)$$

$$\theta_{l,k}^i \leq \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i, \forall l, i, k, i \neq l, \quad (10d)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 \leq P_{\text{max},l}, \forall l. \quad (10e)$$

The constraints (10d) are called consistency constraints. There are in total the $2L(L-1)K$ consistency variables $\theta_{l,k}^i$ and $\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i, \forall k, i, l$, thus (10) involves the $LK(2LK-1)$ optimization variables. Besides, we stress that (8) and (10) are equivalent since $\theta_{l,k}^i = \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i$ at the optimum. The dual decomposition approach is used to decompose problem (10) into L subproblems that can be solved locally. To that end, a partial Lagrangian

¹A function f is strictly convex if for two variables $x_1 \neq x_2$ in the feasible domain of f and a scalar $\alpha \in (0,1)$ makes $\alpha x_1 + (1-\alpha)x_2$ also in the feasible domain, then $f(\alpha x_1 + (1-\alpha)x_2) < \alpha f(x_1) + (1-\alpha)f(x_2)$.

function, which is related to the differences between the consistency variables, is formed as

$$\mathcal{L}(\{\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}, \lambda_{l,k}^i\}) = \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L \lambda_{l,k}^i (\theta_{l,k}^i - \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i) \right), \quad (11)$$

where $\lambda_{l,k}^i \geq 0$ is the Lagrange multiplier associated with the constraint $\theta_{l,k}^i \leq \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i$. The dual function of (11) is computed as the superposition of the L local dual functions

$$g(\{\lambda_{l,k}^i\}) = \sum_{l=1}^L g_l(\{\lambda_{l,k}^i\}), \quad (12)$$

where the local dual function of BS l , $g_l(\{\lambda_{l,k}^i\})$, is

$$\underset{\{\tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \geq 0, \theta_{l,k}^i \geq 0, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i \geq 0\}}{\text{inf}} \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^i \theta_{l,k}^i - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i). \quad (13)$$

From (13), problem (10) can be decomposed into the L subproblems and the l th subproblem is

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{\tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \geq 0, \theta_{l,k}^i \geq 0, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i \geq 0\}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^i \theta_{l,k}^i - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i) \\ & \text{subject to} \quad \frac{G\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^l}{\sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L (\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i)^2 + \sigma_{\text{DL}}^2} \geq \hat{\xi}_{l,k}, \forall k, \\ & \quad G\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2\gamma_{l,k}^l + \sum_{t=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,t}^2 z_{l,k}^t \leq (\theta_{l,k}^i)^2, \forall i, k, i \neq l, \\ & \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 \leq P_{\text{max},l}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Notice that BS l only needs the l th subproblem using $K(2L-1)$ optimization variables, while all the L problems can be processed in parallel by the L BSs for the given values of all Lagrange multipliers $\lambda_{l,k}^i$. The globally optimal solution to (14) is obtained due to its convexity as stated in Theorem 1.

Theorem 1. *The optimization problem (14) is equivalent to the following second-order cone (SOC) program*

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\{\tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \geq 0, s_l, \{\theta_{l,k}^i \geq 0, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i \geq 0\}}{\text{minimize}} \quad s_l \\ & \text{subject to} \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{l,k}\| \leq \tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \sqrt{\frac{G\gamma_{l,k}^l}{\hat{\xi}_{l,k}}}, \forall k, \\ & \quad \|\mathbf{u}_l\| \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + s_l + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i - \lambda_{l,k}^i \theta_{l,k}^i) \right), \\ & \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{i,k}^l\| \leq \theta_{l,k}^i, \forall i, k, i \neq l, \\ & \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{u}}_l\| \leq \sqrt{P_{\text{max},l}}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{l,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{K+L}$, $\mathbf{u}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{K+1}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{l,k}^l \in \mathbb{C}^{K+1}$, and $\check{\mathbf{u}}_l \in \mathbb{C}^K$ are respectively defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{l,k} &= \left[\sqrt{z_{l,k}^l} (\tilde{\rho}_{l,1}, \dots, \tilde{\rho}_{l,K}), \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^1, \dots, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{l-1}, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{l+1}, \dots, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^L, \sigma_{\text{DL}} \right]^T, \\ \mathbf{u}_l &= \left[\tilde{\rho}_{l,1}, \dots, \tilde{\rho}_{l,K}, \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - s_l + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1, \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^l \theta_{l,k}^l - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i) \right) \right]^T, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{l,k}^l &= \left[\tilde{\rho}_{l,k} \sqrt{G \gamma_{l,k}^l}, \sqrt{z_{l,k}^l} (\tilde{\rho}_{l,1}, \dots, \tilde{\rho}_{l,K}) \right]^T, \\ \check{\mathbf{u}}_l &= [\tilde{\rho}_{l,1}, \dots, \tilde{\rho}_{l,K}]^T. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Utilizing the epi-graph representation [15], the objective function of (14) turns to the following constraint by introducing a new optimization variable s_l ,

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1, \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^l \theta_{l,k}^l - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i) \leq s_l, \quad (16)$$

and it is equivalent to

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^2 \leq s_l - \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1, \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^l \theta_{l,k}^l - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i). \quad (17)$$

By applying the identity $x - y = \frac{1}{4}(1+x-y)^2 - \frac{1}{4}(1-x+y)^2$, i.e., with $x = s_l$ and $y = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1, \\ i \neq l}}^L (\lambda_{l,k}^l \theta_{l,k}^l - \lambda_{l,k}^i \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i)$, for the right-hand side of (17), this constraint can be converted to a SOC constraint. The other constraints of (14) can be easily converted to the corresponding SOC constraints as in (15). \square

At the $n+1$ iteration, after obtaining the optimal solutions to the L subproblems in (15), every BS will update those Lagrange multipliers by utilizing the so-called master level thanks to the following master dual problem

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{maximize}_{\{\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n+1)} \geq 0\}} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq l}}^L \lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n+1)} \left(\theta_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)} - \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $\theta_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)}$ and $\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)}$ are the global optimums in the n th iteration to the L subproblems in (15). The subgradient projection method [5] can be adopted to solve problem (18), so the Lagrangian multipliers are updated as

$$\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n+1)} = \left[\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n)} - \zeta^{(n)} \left(\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)} - \theta_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)} \right) \right]_+, \quad \forall l, i, k, \quad (19)$$

where $\zeta^{(n)}$ is a positive step-size at the n th iteration and $[\cdot]_+$ is the projection onto the nonnegative orthant. If the master problem is solved at an arbitrary BS, it acquires the $2K(L-1)^2$ consistency parameters from the $L-1$ remaining BSs. The $2K(L-1)$ updated Lagrange multiplier $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n)}$ and $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n)}$, $\forall i, l, k, i \neq L$ should be sent back BS l . In total, the number of exchanged parameters for each iteration should be $4K(L-1)^2$. The proposed distributed implementation of

Algorithm 1 Distributed implementation for problem (8)

Input: $P_{\max,l}, \forall l$; $\xi_{l,k}, \forall l, k$; $\beta_{l,k}^i, \forall l, i, k$; Initial Lagrange multipliers $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(1)}, \forall l, i, k$; Set up $n = 1$ and $\zeta^{(1)}$.

1. *Iteration n:*

- 1.1. BS l solves problem (15) utilizing $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n)}$ from the master level.
- 1.2. Send $\tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)}$ and $\theta_{l,k}^{i,*,(n)}$, $\forall l, i, k$, to the master level
- 1.3. Update $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(n+1)}$ by using (19).
2. If *Stopping criterion is satisfied* \rightarrow *Stop*. Otherwise, go to Step 3.
3. Restore the currently optimal powers: $\rho_{l,k}^{*,(n)} = \tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^{*,(n)}, \forall l, k$. Set $n = n + 1$ and update $\zeta^{(n+1)}$, then go to Step 1.

Output: The optimal solutions: $\rho_{l,k}^* = \rho_{l,k}^{(n)}, \forall l, k$.

problem (8) is presented in Algorithm 1. Furthermore, the convergence property of Algorithm 1 is effectively stated in the following theorem.

Theorem 2. *The distributed implementation in Algorithm 1 is able to yield the optimal solution to (8).*

Proof. The constraint functions of problem (15) are strictly convex, so the solution to the master dual problem (18) converges to the global optimum with $\theta_{l,k}^i - \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i \rightarrow 0, \forall l, i, k$, if the step-size $\zeta^{(n)}$ is small enough [4], [16]. Consequently, the centralized and distributed implementation have the same optimal solution. \square

C. *Complexity Analysis of (15)*

Since problem (15) contains SOC constraints, a standard interior-point method (IPM) [17], [18] can be used to find its optimal solution. The worst-case runtime of the IPM is computed as follows.

Definition 1: For a given tolerance $\epsilon > 0$, the set of $\tilde{\rho}_{l,k}^\epsilon, s_l^\epsilon, \theta_{l,k}^{l,\epsilon}, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^{l,\epsilon}$ is called an ϵ -solution to problem (15) if $s_l^\epsilon \leq s_l^* + \epsilon$, where s_l^* is the globally optimal solution to the optimization problem (15).

The number of decision variables of problem (15) is on the order of $m = \mathcal{O}(K(2L-1) + 1)$ where $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ represents the big-O notation, thus we introduce Lemma 2.

Lemma 2. *The computational complexity to obtain ϵ -solution to problem (15) is*

$$\delta (LK^3 + 6LK^2 + KL^2 + 6LK + 3K + 5 + m^2) m, \quad (20)$$

where $\delta = \ln(\epsilon^{-1})\sqrt{2LK+4}$.

Proof. First, problem (15) has K SOC constraints of dimension $(K+L+1)$, $(L-1)K+1$ SOC constraints of dimension $(K+2)$, and 1 SOC constraints of dimension $(K+1)$. Based on these observations, one can follow the same steps as in [19, Section V-A] to arrive at (20). Note that the term δ in (20) is the iteration complexities required for obtaining ϵ -solution to problem (15) while the remaining terms represent the per-iteration computation costs [19]. \square

TABLE I: The total number of optimization variables and exchanged variables for the considered approaches

Method	Execution Place	Total Number of Opt. variables	Total Number of Ex. Parameters
Centralized Imp.	Core Network	KL	$2KL^2 + 2KL$
Basic form of Distributed Imp.	Base Stations	KL^2	$2K(L-1)^2L + K(L-1)L$
Distributed Imp. by Dual Decomp.	Base Stations	$2KL^2 - KL + L$	$4K(L-1)^2N + 2K(L-1)L$

D. Comparison of Centralized and Distributed Implementation Approaches

Table I summarizes the total number of the optimization variables and the exchanged parameters for the centralized and distributed implementations. Even though the distributed approach utilizing dual decomposition divides (8) into the L subproblems where every BS can locally optimize the power control coefficients, it also introduces the new optimization variables leading to the highest amount of the optimization variables. The total number of exchanged parameters may be less than in the basic form of distributed implementation because N is usually small as shown in Section IV. Furthermore, for a subset of user locations where the number of iterations needed for the distributed approach (i.e., denoted by N in Table I) increases, the number of exchanged parameters may surpass that of the centralized implementation. Unlike the small-scale networks, in Massive MIMO, the distributed implementation by dual decomposition does not bring exchanged information reduction compared to the centralized counterpart since the burden which comes from small-scale fading has been mitigated by virtues of the channel hardening and favorable propagation properties [1].

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We consider a wrapped-around cellular network with $L = 4$, $M = 500$, $\tau_c = 200$, $P_{\max,l} = 40$ W, $\hat{p}_{l,k} = 200$ mW, and $\xi_{l,k} = 0.5$ b/s/Hz, $\forall l, k$. The KL users are randomly distributed over the network coverage area with uniform distribution. The distance of user k in cell l to BS l is denoted as $d_{l,k}^l$ km and $d_{l,k}^l \geq 0.035$ km. The system bandwidth and noise figure are 20 MHz and -96 dBm, respectively. The large-scale fading coefficient is modeled as

$$\beta_{l,k}^l [dB] = -148.1 - 37.6 \log_{10}(d_{l,k}^l) + z_{l,k}, \quad (21)$$

where the shadow fading $z_{l,k}$ follows a log-normal Gaussian distribution with standard variation 7 dB. The Lagrange multipliers are initially selected as $\lambda_{l,k}^{i,(1)} = 0, \forall l, i, k$, while the step size in (19) is defined as $\zeta^{(n)} = 0.01$. ZF precoding is used for simulations. Monte-Carlo results are obtained over 1000 different realizations of user locations.

Fig. 2 shows the probability of the number of iterations which Algorithm 1 needs to obtain the 95% of the global optimum for (a) $K = 1$ and (b) $K = 10$. Algorithm 1

Fig. 2: Distribution of the number of iterations utilizing Algorithm 1 at the 95% of the global optimum: (a), $K = 1$; (b), $K = 10$.

Fig. 3: Actual QoS [b/s/Hz] of each user at the 95% of the global optimum.

converges to the desired objective value after a few iterations. For example, with $K = 10$, 12.4% of user locations only need 1 iterations to attain the 95% global optimum. If we set 400 iterations as a maximum level to terminate the algorithm for the realizations of users which are in trouble to obtain the 95% global optimum, there are 1.4% of the user realizations facing with this issue. Meanwhile, by comparing Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b, we observe that Algorithm 1 requires more iterations to converge to the global optimum when increasing the number of users in the network.

Fig. 3 gives the cumulative distribution probability (CDF) of the actual QoS per user at the 95% global optimum. The results confirm that the proposed distributed implementation obtains the QoS requirements for most of the users. However, the performance gap between the proposed algorithm and its centralized counterpart is wider as the number of users increases.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a distributed algorithm where every BS can independently and simultaneously minimize its transmit powers thanks to the Lagrange multipliers $\{\lambda_{l,k}^i\}$ provided by the central entity, while a subset of nominal parameters pre-

senting the strength of mutual interference $\{\theta_{l,k}^i, \tilde{\theta}_{l,k}^i\}$ should be sent back to the central entity to update these Lagrange multipliers. The distributed algorithm utilizing dual decomposition converges to the global optimum obtained by the centralized counterpart in most of the realizations of user locations after a few iterations of updating these Lagrange multipliers. Unlike the small-scale MIMO networks, for the multi-cell Massive MIMO systems, the distributed implementation does not bring a significant reduction of the exchanged information between BSs in comparison to the centralized counterpart.

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